

A facile superoxide induced conversion of aromatic amines to azo compounds under microwave irradiation

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Abstract : The present report demonstrates an efficient use of tetraethylammonium superoxide under non-aqueous conditions to bring about a mild and convenient transformation of aromatic amines to azo compounds in good yield under mono-mode microwave irradiation.

Keywords : Tetraethylammonium superoxide, amines, azo compounds.

Introduction

Aromatic azo compounds are high-value chemicals widely used as organic dyes, pigments, food additives, radical reaction initiators and therapeutic agents¹. In addition, azo derivatives are also found to have the potential for use in electronic and drug delivery applications². A variety of oxidation methods have been reported for the preparation of these compounds. For example, aromatic amines can be oxidized with oxidants such as peracetic acid, manganese dioxide, lead tetraacetate, Hg(OAc)₂, barium manganate, phenyl iodoacetate, sodium hypochlorite, potassium ferricyanide, potassium ferrate, barium ferrate monohydrate, and mercury(II) oxide³. Most of these methods are based on stoichiometric processes and frequently environmentally unfriendly transition metals⁴. The oxidation of aromatic amines particularly diamines has also been effected using four fold excess of potassium superoxide⁵. A sustainable chemical process for an efficient synthesis of aromatic azo compounds under non-aqueous conditions is thus of practical importance.

Microwave irradiation⁶ with the use of non-toxic reagents, provides a clean chemical process with an advantageous merit of enhanced reaction rates, higher yields, greater selectivity, and ease of manipulation. In view of the above and as a part of our ongoing research on superoxide chemistry⁷, we wish to report herein a convenient application of environmentally benign MW-superoxide ion combination for an efficient oxidation of anilines under non-aqueous conditions with reasonably good yields (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In the present course of reaction, tetraethylammonium superoxide was generated *in situ* by the phase transfer reaction of KO₂ and Et₄NBr in dry DMF at room temperature and was subsequently allowed to react with aromatic amines **1** under microwave irradiation.

In order to optimize the reaction conditions, a typical reaction of aniline (**1a**), was carried out in the presence of superoxide under microwave irradiation at different power (Watt), temperature and time in DMF. The outcome is given in Table 1. It is evident from the table that the use of the microwave-superoxide combination brings

Table 1. Effect of MW on the reaction of superoxide and aniline **1a**

Entry	Microwave			
	MW (Watt)	Temp (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	100	60	5	50
2	100	80	5	57
3	120	60	7	54
4	120	80	5	68
5	120	100	5	67
6	180	60	5	58
7	180	80	5	66
8	180	100	5	66

about an efficient conversion of aniline to azobenzene in a very short time, the best result being obtained using 120 W at 80 °C in 5 min in the presence of tetraethylammonium superoxide (*cf.* entry 4).

Under the optimized set of reaction conditions (entry 4), a number of aromatic amines **1** were allowed to undergo oxidation under controlled microwave (120 W, 80 °C) heating. The results are given in Table 2.

As an outcome, azo compounds **2a-j** are readily formed

In conclusion, tetraethylammonium superoxide brings about an efficient and easy conversion of amines to azo compounds under controlled microwave irradiation. The present approach makes use of equimolar proportion of KO_2 and affords the product in very short reaction time.

Experimental

Potassium superoxide and tetraethylammonium bromide were procured from E. Merck, and were used as

Table 2. Reaction of $\text{KO}_2/\text{Et}_4\text{NBr}$ with aromatic amines **1**

Sl. no.	Reactants (1)	Products (2)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C) (Lit. ⁸ m.p.)
a	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5$	68	67–68 (68)
b	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{-}p$	71	142 (143)
c	$o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$	$o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{-}o$	72	53–55 (54)
d	$p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$	$p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}p$	48	184–185 (185)
e	$p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$	$p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br-}p$	50	203–205 (205)
f	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3\text{-}p$	79	160–161 (160)
g	$o\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$	$o\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3\text{-}o$	76	142 (143)
h	1-Naphthylamine	1-Azonaphthalene	68	189–191 (190)
i	$2,4\text{-Cl}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_2$	$2,4\text{-Cl}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Cl}_2\text{-}2,4$	45	162–164 (164–166)
J	$2,4,6\text{-Br}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{NH}_2$	$2,4,6\text{-Br}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_2\text{Br}_3\text{-}2,4,6$	44	214–215 (217–218)

in 44–79% yield. Both the electron donating and electron withdrawing groups in the aromatic ring worked well, although the yield in the case of electron withdrawing groups is little low. A molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 0.5 for substrate **1** : KO_2 : Et_4NBr was employed for achieving the reaction.

Contrary to the earlier report⁵, the present approach makes use of equimolar proportion of the reactant and KO_2 in the presence of phase transfer catalyst under controlled MW irradiation. Various substituted aromatic amines are made to react smoothly under the present set of reaction conditions in dramatically reduced reaction time. Each reaction was monitored by TLC for its completion. The products were identified by their physical and spectral data, which were in full agreement with the reported values. The disappearance of N–H stretching bands at 3509–3460 and 3416–3382 cm^{-1} and the appearance of a strong absorption band between 1630–1575 cm^{-1} due to -N=N- stretching, clearly showed that amino compounds have been oxidized to azo compounds. Further the characteristic exchangeable aromatic amines absorption signal at $\sim\delta$ 5.0–3.0 is invariably not observed in the products.

received. Dry DMF of Aldrich, was stored over molecular sieves (4 Å) prior to use. Melting points were measured in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were run on a JEOL AL300FT-NMR and chemical shift are expressed as δ/ppm , using TMS as internal reference. The microwave irradiation was effected using the CEM's Discover Bench Mate single-mode microwave synthesis system using safe pressure regulation 10-mL pressurized vials with "snap-on" cap.

General procedure for the reaction of in situ generated tetraethylammonium superoxide with aromatic amines :

Potassium superoxide (0.28 g; 0.004 mol) and tetraethylammonium bromide (0.42 g; 0.002 mol) were weighted under nitrogen atmosphere using an atmosbag and were transferred into a pressure regulation 10-mL pressurized vials with "snap-on" cap. Dry dimethylformamide (5 mL) was added to it and the mixture was agitated magnetically for 15 min to facilitate the formation of tetraethylammonium superoxide. To the stirred reaction mixture, were added aromatic amine **1** (0.004 mol). The "snap-on" cap was put in and the reaction

vessel was irradiated at 120 W for 5 min. After the reaction was over (as indicated by TLC), mixture was treated with brine solution (2 mL) followed by saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (2 mL) and then extracted with diethyl ether (2 × 10 mL). The combined organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄ (anhyd.), filtered and evaporated to give the product **2**, which was purified by recrystallization.

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